

Customized EdgeCloudSim: Enhanced Mobility and Network Models for Urban Vehicular Edge Computing

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Abstract— An important challenge in edge computing service management is maintaining good quality of service and low latency for end-users. Edge services must be hosted near the end user, necessitating sophisticated management of virtualized resources in the edge infrastructure. In the context of edge computing, users' location and mobility patterns are essential components of resource allocation and service transfer. As a result, it is of the utmost importance to assess the effectiveness of the proposed management solutions in a city environment with realistic mobility. The purpose of this study is to investigate the simulation of edge computing and to present an integrated solution environment that makes use of two validated simulators for the modeling of urban mobility and edge computing services.

Keywords— Vehicular edge computing, simulators, mobility modelling, EdgeCloudSim, SUMO

I. INTRODUCTION

For applications like real-time high-resolution video streaming and autonomous driving, 5G technology requires a lot of computational power and advanced networking. These criteria lead to a mutually beneficial relationship between 5G networks and Multi Access Edge Computing (MEC) architecture [1]. To minimize the delay in data transmission, it is essential to implement the Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) architecture and position the processing and storage resources near the access points of the 5G wireless network [2]. Our focus in the paper is on scenarios that are densely populated with a variety of actors, such as pedestrians, vehicles, bicycles, and public transportation, all of which follow the standard norms that govern movement in urban settings. Several simulators are available for cloud/edge computing scenarios. These simulators are used to create computational models for virtualized cloud environments, considering factors such as CPU, memory, storage, and energy consumption. In our work [3] we reviewed different simulators for edge cloud continuum however, none of these methods allow the development of complex mobility models for the end-devices. From this point of view, we investigate the possibility of combining two well-known tools: EdgeCloudSim [4], which has been improved with its mobility and network models to offer support for MEC services, and SUMO [5], which is designed to generate realistic simulation scenarios for 5G MEC services. Together, these tools allow researchers to concentrate on MEC-focused

study while benefiting from results analysis based on intricate mobility scenarios. The existing version of the EdgeCloudSim utilizes the nomadic mobility model, which is not realistic. This motivated us to enhance it by integrating vehicle movements generated by SUMO. In particular, the following contributions have been led out in the paper: 1. We have extended the default mobility model by using SUMO to generate realistic patterns of vehicle movements. 2. We have used realistic positions of 5G base stations located in the city of Cosenza as our edge data centers. 3. We have implemented a realistic 5G channel model based on the Close-in (CI) path loss model which computes dynamic propagation delay based on path loss and distance between vehicles and edge data centers. The paper is organized as follows: section II highlights the existing research related to workload orchestrators for vehicular edge computing; section III provides the description of the integrated simulation environment with the improved mobility and network models; challenges and overcomes are presented in section IV and the conclusions are summarized in the last section.

II. EXISTING RESEARCH ON WORKLOAD ORCHESTRATION FOR VEHICULAR EDGE COMPUTING

VEC systems utilize various features, with task offloading being one of the most crucial. The challenge of determining where to offload tasks can be addressed through workload orchestration, which has been explored for edge computing systems. Cao et al. [6] studied methods for task allocation in MEC designs, finding that traditional approaches work well in static or slowly changing environments but struggle in dynamic mobile networks. Ning et al. [7] proposed a DRL-based solution, which, despite its effectiveness, faces challenges due to the dynamic configurations and fluctuating network resources in VEC systems. Sun et al. [8] introduced ALTO, an adaptive learning-based task offloading technique that employs Multi-Armed Bandit theory to optimize data transfer times in dynamic VEC environments. Wang et al. [9] used game theory to calculate offloading probabilities in vehicular MEC networks. Liu et al. [10] employed matching theory to minimize network latency in task offloading, leveraging its ability to provide decentralized solutions for complex network topologies. Wang et al. [11] proposed a federated offloading technique that divides tasks into local processing, V2I communication, and V2V communication.

Dai et al. [12] discussed the challenges of server overload in VEC systems, proposing a combination of load balancing and offloading techniques as a mixed integer nonlinear programming problem. Sonmez et al. [13] developed a two-stage vehicular edge orchestrator that uses machine learning to optimize task completion and service time, though their approach has limitations, such as oversimplified traffic models and communication channels. Inspired by this last work, we extended the default EdgeCloudSim mobility model by integrating it with SUMO and enhancing the network model with a realistic 5G channel model that accounts for dynamic propagation delays based on the distance between transmitter and receiver.

Fig. 1 SUMO and EdgeCloudSim integration process

III. A SIMULATOR FOR EDGE/CLOUD ENVIRONMENT

EdgeCloudSim is a versatile simulation framework designed to model multitier scenarios, including network modeling for WLAN and WAN, device mobility, and load generation. It simulates the coordination of multiple edge servers with top-layer cloud solutions, leveraging CloudSim for tasks like creating virtual machines. However, for accurate vehicular edge computing (VEC) simulations, enhancements were made to EdgeCloudSim by integrating a realistic mobility model and a 5G channel model. The diagram in Figure 1 illustrates a detailed procedure we have adopted for modeling vehicular edge computing (VEC) by employing SUMO (Simulation of Urban Mobility) and EdgeCloudSim. The integration process involves three steps. First, Vodafone base station data for Cosenza, Italy, was obtained from <https://lteitaly.it/>, selecting five base stations with their latitude and longitude, as given in Figure 2. This data was used with SUMO to generate floating car data (FCD), stored in an XML file that details vehicle movements over time. The FCD was then used to update or establish edge data centers within the simulation, ensuring realistic positioning of edge devices and accurate vehicular mobility modeling. In the final stage, simulation configuration and execution involve setting up files like *edge_devices.xml* and *applications.xml*. EdgeCloudSim's components, such as the *VehicularScenarioFactory*, *VehicularNetworkModel*, and *VehicularEdgeOrchestrator*, manage different aspects of the simulation, including network configurations, orchestration decisions, and resource allocation. The simulation models VEC scenarios using 5G, WLAN, WAN, and MAN networks, providing a comprehensive and realistic framework for studying edge computing in vehicular environments.

Fig. 2 Vodafone 5G Base Stations on Cosenza Map

A. extension of mobility of model in edgecloudsim

The *VehicularMobilityModel.java* class is responsible for tracking vehicle positions during a simulation. Its main methods are *Initialize* and *getLocation*. The *Initialize* method retrieves Floating Car Data (FCD) at the start of the simulation using the *FCDReader* class, which reads vehicle movement data generated by SUMO. The process begins by creating an empty list to hold vehicle objects. The *FCD* class reads an XML document containing vehicle data, such as vehicle ID and location coordinates, and creates *TimeStep* objects for each vehicle. These objects are used to generate vehicle objects, which are then linked to the nearest edge data center. The unique vehicle IDs are added to the *TimeStep*, and the list of vehicle objects is returned. The *getLocation* method retrieves and logs the geographic coordinates of a vehicle at a specified simulation time. It requires two parameters: *deviceId* (the vehicle's unique identifier) and *time*. The method identifies the corresponding vehicle object, searches through the *TimeStep* list to find the specified time, and retrieves the vehicle's coordinates. It then calculates the nearest edge data center using the *getNearestDataCenterByPower* method, which considers the power threshold, and updates the vehicle's position in the database with its coordinates and WLAN ID. The method returns a *Location* object that includes the location index, WLAN ID, and coordinates. To calculate the distance between a vehicle and an edge data center, the class first determines the number of data centers within a one-kilometer radius of the vehicle. It then calculates the power from each data center using a path loss formula. If the power level meets a predetermined threshold, the vehicle is assigned the WLAN ID of the corresponding edge data center. The method iterates over all edge data centers within one kilometer to assign the appropriate WLAN ID.

B. Simulations for the Mobility Model Class

Initially, the task is passed to the *getDeviceToOffload* method, which is defined in the *VehicularEdgeOrchestrator* class, to retrieve the device ID. The device ID specifies the destination for the task transfer, which can be either the edge data center, or cloud data center via RSU or cloud data center via 5G cellular network for offloading the task. Whereas we find the nearest edge data center on the basis of signal strength of the edge data center within range of one kilometer and edge datacenter is selected which has higher signal strength. We performed the simulations taking one vehicle into considering which moves into the map extracted from the SUMO, and five edge data centers, the vehicle is assigned to the edge data center or base station ID on the bases of signal strength

received from the base station which varies with the distance as shown in Figure 5.

Fig.3. The procedure of the Floating Car Data (FCD) class

Fig.4. Mobility Model Class

The signal strength decreases when the distance between vehicle and edge data center increases. Obviously, path loss also increases with distance as shown in Figure 6. Figure 7 shows the decrease of signal strength over the increase in path loss component when the distance between vehicle and edge data center increases.

C. Extension of the edgecloudsim network model

In EdgeCloudSim, a single server queuing model is used to simulate various communication standards, including WLAN, MAN, WAN, and GSM-based cellular networks. This is done through a wrapper class that manages the behavior of these communication standards, handling details such as task size and transmission delay using the MMP/M/1 queuing model, which considers both the Poisson arrival rate and task size. However, the existing GSM model in EdgeCloudSim oversimplifies real-world GSM network

behavior, leading to inaccurate representations of propagation delays and network unpredictability.

Fig. 5 Signal strength variations for edge data center over distance

Fig.6 Path loss component over distance

Fig.7 Signal strength variations over path loss

To address this, the simple GSM model was replaced with a 5G model incorporating the CI path loss model, which provides a more realistic simulation by considering factors like frequency, distance, and a realistic path loss exponent. This enhancement significantly improves the accuracy of latency estimates and supports more informed decisions regarding task offloading, particularly in modern urban environments. The equation used in the CI model is given in Equation 1. Where n is the path loss exponent and $\chi_{CI}\sigma$ is the shadow fading standard deviation and d is the distance between transmitter and receiver. The term PL_{CI} stands for Path Loss in Free Space, which is the reduction in signal power between a transmitter and receiver when they are 1 meter apart at the carrier frequency f . The Close In (CI) path is more reliable when applied for different frequencies. To simplify calculations and ensure consistency over a wide range of scenarios, the model is primarily dependent on the path loss exponent (PLE). There is a possibility that the signal strength along a particular path will be diminished due to obstructions such as buildings, trees, and other barriers. Using the Close-in (CI) path loss model's standard deviation improves signal estimation. Within the context of the CI Path

Loss Model, our simulation utilized the Urban Micro-Cellular (UMi) Street Canyon (SC) scenario. It really depicts congested, challenging urban conditions used in vehicle edge computing systems. The CI model considers many elements. These include path loss exponent (PLE=3.1), shadow fading standard deviation (SF=8.1dB), and non-line-of-sight conditions.

$$PLCI(f, d)[dB]=FSPL(f, 1m)[dB]+10\eta\log_{10}(d)+\chi CI\sigma \quad (1)$$

$$FSPL(f, 1m)[dB]=20\log_{10}(c4\pi f) \quad (2)$$

Symbols	Description
$\chi CI\sigma$	shadow fading standard deviation
η	Path loss exponent
π	3.142
f	frequency
d	distance between transmitter and receiver
c	Speed of light

D. Computation of 5G download/upload delay

Finding out the delays that 5G networks experience during data uploading and downloading is achieved by using both the *get5GDownloadDelay* and *get5GUploadDelay* methods. One of the factors determining the effectiveness of these systems is an effective bandwidth, which is changed based on path loss estimates. The *calculateDistance* function is being used to determine the distance between the origin and the destination. The Haversine formula is utilized to calculate the distance between the vehicle and the edge data center. The average delay is computed in the method *calculateMM1* which takes task size and effective bandwidth as an input parameter. The delay is obtained by combining propagation delay and queuing delay.

IV. SIMULATORS INTEGRATION CHALLENGES OVERCOME

SUMO supports OpenStreetMap but does not include information about Edge Datacenters. To create a realistic simulation, a dataset of BTS/Edge devices was obtained from <https://lteitaly.it/> and converted into a POI Poly file. Since EdgeCloudSim lacks SUMO support or integration, Floating Car Data (FCD) from SUMO simulations was used to model vehicle mobility, and EdgeCloudSim's mobility class was modified accordingly. While EdgeCloudSim typically allows linear vehicle movement along the x-axis with the y-axis fixed at zero, SUMO FCD was employed to capture individual vehicle movements at specific times. However, EdgeCloudSim generates tasks at different intervals than SUMO moves vehicles, leading to synchronization issues. To resolve this, the LoadGeneratorModel was modified to produce tasks based on SUMO Floating Car Data, ensuring that task generation and vehicle movement are synchronized. Moreover, since EdgeCloudSim generates tasks in a stochastic environment, making it difficult to estimate task generation per vehicle accurately, a system was implemented to produce a predetermined number of tasks per second. Finally, while EdgeCloudSim originally has 40 standard datacenters positioned at fixed locations along the x-axis (ranging from zero to 400), these were replaced with Vodafone's 5G base

stations in Cosenza, Italy, providing accurate latitude and longitude information for edge devices in the simulation.

CONCLUSIONS

This study has focused on the importance of workload orchestrators and the challenges they present in the context of vehicle edge computing systems. We investigated the simulation of edge computing and to present an integrated solution environment that makes use of two validated simulators for the modeling of urban mobility and edge computing services. The default mobility model has been extended using SUMO to generate realistic vehicle movements, using Cosenza's 5G base stations as edge data centers. A realistic 5G channel model is implemented using the Close-in path loss model, which computes dynamic propagation delay based on path loss and vehicle distance. A realistic 5G channel model has been incorporated into the network model of the EdgeCloudSim simulator, and the mobility model of the simulator has been extended via SUMO integration.

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